

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSES ON VIBRATION PATTERNS OF RECTANGULAR COMPOSITE LAMINATE WITH THROUGH-THE-WIDTH DELAMINATION

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ABSTRACT

Nondestructive evaluation plays the critical role in durability and reliability assessment of the advanced composite structures. In the present paper, vibration pattern imaging technique and finite element method are applied to characterize the dynamic response of the rectangular composite laminates with through-the-width delamination. A simple delamination model for finite element analysis was proposed and applied to the analysis of the eigenfrequency and the modal patterns of the delaminated specimen. Laser Doppler vibrometer was applied to non-contacting transducer for the measurement of the vibration of the specimen. The agreement between the numerical and experimental results was very good and the results indicate that the size and location of the delamination have complicated effect upon the eigenfrequency and the modal patterns.

Keywords: nondestructive evaluation, vibration, delamination, laser Doppler vibrometer, finite element analysis, modal analysis, eigenfrequency

1. INTRODUCTION

In the service condition, nondestructive evaluation plays the critical role in durability and reliability assessment of the advanced composite structures[1]. Though, acoustic emission[2], ultrasonic inspection [3] and other methods have been developed for the detection and evaluation of the damages, there exist some problems in their applicability to the composite structures with complicated shape and thick members, such as sandwich structure. Recently, vibration pattern imaging technique has been developed by using the laser Doppler vibrometer. The method seems to be promising for detecting the change of the eigenfrequency and modal shape due to the damages. In the present paper, vibration of rectangular composite plate with through-the-width delamination was investigated by using the laser Doppler vibrometer, VPI900, and the finite element method in order to discuss the applicability of the vibration pattern imaging technique to the non-destructive estimation of composite structure.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SUBJECT

Materials are unidirectional, $[0]_s$, and quasi-isotropic, $[45/-45/0/90]_s$, carbon/epoxy laminate with the average fiber volume fraction, V_f , of 57%. The nominal thickness is 1.25 mm. The elastic moduli of the unidirectional carbon/epoxy lamina are as follows;

$$E_L = 112 \text{ GPa}, E_T = 7.75 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{LT} = 0.34, G_{LT} = G_{ZL} = 4.66 \text{ GPa}, G_{TZ} = 2.85 \text{ GPa}$$

Specimen is a rectangular plate with through-the-width delamination, as schematically shown in Figure 1. Width, W , and length, L , of the specimen are 75 mm and 400 mm, respectively. In order to model a delamination, single 12.5 μm thick PTFE film is inserted in the midplane of the laminate. The length of the artificial delamination, a , is 100 mm.

Rotation and displacement of one end of the specimen is fixed. The boundary condition of the other end and both edges are free as shown in the figure. A coordinate, (x,y,z) , system is defined as the directions of x , y and z axes coincide with the longitudinal, transverse and through-the-thickness directions on the specimen, respectively. Location of the delamination is measured as the distance, d , from the fixed end to the center line of the delamination as shown in Figure 1.

3. NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

Dynamic eigenvalue analysis was carried out by using the finite element analysis code, MARC k3 version. An isoparametric 8-node thick shell element was employed for finite element modeling of the specimen. The elastic properties of the shell element was calculated from the lamina properties based on the lamination theory. The delaminated region was modeled as a pair of shells with the upper and lower layup, for example, $[45/-45/0/90]_T$ and $[90/0/-45/45]_T$ of the quasi-isotropic laminate. The gap and thickness of the shell is equal to half of the undelaminated laminate. As the result the effect of the contact of the delamination surfaces was not considered in the present analysis. Lanczos method is used to extract the eigenvalues and eigenvectors. An example of the mesh division is shown in Figure 2. Total number of mesh for the delaminated model is 216.

Figure 1 Rectangular specimen with through-the-width delamination

Figure 2 Mesh division of the delaminated specimen

4. EXPERIMENT

Laser Doppler vibrometer was applied to non-contacting transducer for the measurement of the vibration of the specimen. VPI 9000 system, developed and manufactured by Ometron Ltd., U. K., was used for the present experiment. Single-beam back scatter arrangement is adopted, and light reflected back from the specimen surface is shifted in frequency by an amount $2v/\lambda$, where v is the velocity of the specimen surface and λ is the wavelength of the laser radiation. For a helium-neon laser at 633 nm, the frequency shift is 3.16 MHz per m/s velocity. Data acquisition is under computer control and scan are produced in a raster-like manner in VPI 9000 system. Full field images of vibration pattern permits correlation between experimental and computational methods on the basis of similar degrees of freedom.

The fixed end of the specimen was mounted to the vibrator and the out-of-plane vibration was applied to the end of the specimen. An accelerometer was attached to the loading point and the input signal was monitored. The delamination was located on the center of the specimen, that is, d of 200 mm. Modal analysis based on FFT technique was applied to search the resonance frequency. The accurate resonance frequency was determined by monitoring the vibration pattern and its amplitude with VPI 9000 system.

5. RESULTS

Pure bending and coupled bending and torsional vibrations are observed as schematically shown in Figures 3 (a) and (b). We define the vibration modes by counting the number of the bending and torsional vibration node lines, m and n , respectively. Vibration mode $(m, 0)$, for example, indicates the m -th pure bending mode, and $(m, 1)$ represents coupling of the m -th bending and the first torsional vibration mode. For convenience, we call the $(m, 1)$ mode as the m -th coupled torsional mode because the vibration modes of $(m, 0)$ and $(m, 1)$ are the present interest. According to the present definition, Figure 3 (a) and (b) show the 5-th pure bending mode and the 5-th coupled torsional mode, respectively.

Figure 3 Example of vibration modes

5.1 Experimental Results

Effect of delamination on the eigenfrequencies of the pure bending mode in the unidirectional and quasi-isotropic specimens are listed in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Remarkable frequency reduction due to delamination is observed when the mode number, m , is larger than and equal to 4.

Examples of the pure bending vibration patterns of the unidirectional specimens are shown in Figures 4 - 6 comparing the effect of delamination. Figures 7 - 11 represents the effect of delamination on the pure bending modes and the coupled torsional modes in quasi-isotropic specimens. It is observed in these figures that spacing and shape of node lines are affected by the existence of delamination.

Table 1 Eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes in the unidirectional specimen

Mode No.	Undelaminated (Hz)	Delaminated a=100 (Hz)	Reduction Rate (%)
1	8.58	8.44	1.6
2	74.0	71.4	3.5
3	196.6	164.6	16.3
4	383.0	372.0	2.8
5	635.0	505.0	20.4
6	954.0	791.0	17.1
7	1323.0	1111.0	16.0
8	1767.0	1448.0	18.1

Table 2 Eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Mode No.	Undelaminated (Hz)	Delaminated a=100 (Hz)	Reduction Rate (%)
3	102.6	79.8	22.2
4	206.0	198.1	3.8
5	348.0	271.0	22.1
6	531.0	389.0	26.7
7	746.0	560.0	24.9
8	980.0	753.0	23.2

Figure 4 The third vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 5 The fifth vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 6 The eighth vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 7 The third vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 8 The fifth vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 9 The seventh vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 10 The fourth vibration mode of coupled torsional in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 11 The fifth vibration mode of coupled torsional in the quasi-isotropic specimen

5.2 Numerical Results

Eigenfrequencies of the test specimen are calculated. the results of the pure bending mode of unidirectional and quasi-isotropic specimens are shown in Figure 12 (a) and (b), respectively. The agreement between numerical and experimental results are excellent. Validity of the delamination model adopted in the present paper was confirmed.

Figures 13 - 18 depict the example of pure bending vibration patterns in unidirectional and quasi-isotropic specimen. Effect of delamination on spacing and shape of the node lines are clearly demonstrated in the numerical results. Compared with the experimental results shown in Figures 4 - 9, the numerical results excellently agree with the experimental results. Numerical results of the 4th and 5th coupled torsional modes are shown in Figures 19 and 20. The vibration patterns are in good agreement with the experimental results shown in Figures 10 and 11. The numerical and experimental results indicate that the delamination more directly affects on the vibration patterns in the coupled torsional modes than those in the pure bending modes.

Figure 12 Numerical results of eigenfrequency

Figure 13 Numerical result of the third vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 14 Numerical result of the fifth vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 15 Numerical result of the eighth vibration mode of pure bending in the unidirectional specimen

Figure 16 Numerical result of the third vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 17 Numerical result of the fifth vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 18 Numerical result of the seventh vibration mode of pure bending in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 19 Numerical result of the fourth vibration mode of coupled torsional in the quasi-isotropic specimen

Figure 20 Numerical result of the fifth vibration mode of coupled torsional in the quasi-isotropic specimen

5.3 Parametric Study

Accuracy of the numerical approach was well confirmed by comparing with the experimental results, the parametric study was carried out by changing the configuration of the finite element model. Figures 21 and 22 represent the effect of delamination length on the eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes and coupled torsional modes, respectively, in the unidirectional specimen. As the eigenfrequency increases, the frequency shift becomes more sensitive to the delamination length. The delamination has more direct effect upon the coupled torsional mode than the pure bending mode. The effects of the location on the eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes and the coupled torsional modes are shown in Figure 23 and 24, respectively. The location of the delamination was changed from 50 mm to 350 mm at interval of 50 mm. The delamination length was fixed to 50 mm. Location of the delamination has complicated effect upon the eigenfrequency.

Figure 21 Effect of delamination length on the eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes

Figure 22 Effect of delamination length on the eigenfrequency of the coupled torsional modes

Figure 23 Effect of location of delamination on the eigenfrequency of the pure bending modes

Figure 24 Effect of location of delamination on the eigenfrequency of the coupled torsional modes

Fig 25 Modal pattern of the eighth pure bending mode

6. DISCUSSIONS

Figures 21 and 22 indicate that the detectable delamination length is approximately L/m , where L and m are the specimen length and the mode number, respectively. The location of the delamination also affects the eigenfrequency. Figure 23 indicates that the reduction of the eigenfrequency at d of 350 mm is larger than that at d of 150 mm in the 8th pure bending mode. Figures 25 (a) and (b) represent the modal pattern of the 8th pure bending at the delamination location, d , of 150 mm and 350 mm, respectively. The delamination front at d of 150 mm locates almost on the nodal line and vibration pattern is not affected by the delamination. In the case of the distance is 350 mm, on the other hand, the delamination front locates at the large amplitude region, and the modal shape is disturbed by the delamination.

7. CONCLUSION

Vibration pattern imaging technique and finite element method are applied to characterize the dynamic response of the composite laminates with delamination. A simple delamination model for finite element analysis was proposed and applied to the analysis of the eigenfrequency and the modal patterns of the delaminated specimen. Laser Doppler vibrometer was applied to non-contacting transducer for the measurement of the vibration of the specimen. The effect of delamination on the modal pattern was clearly detected by applying the laser Doppler vibrometer and the imaging technique. The agreement between the numerical and experimental results was very good and the results indicate that the size and location of the delamination have complicated effect upon the eigenfrequency and the modal patterns.

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